

An Autonomous and Intelligent AIS Receiver Station

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Abstract—The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a tracking system for marine traffic monitoring and collision prevention. Vessels transmit their unique identification, position, and voyage information as AIS messages. To improve AIS tracking, two main approaches are possible: (i) to extend the coverage of the network of AIS receiver stations and (ii) to filter out damaged and erroneous AIS messages as early as possible.

In this paper, we discuss the design and implementation of an autonomous AIS receiver station intended to be installed at remote areas on the shore. We describe the station’s hardware consisting of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components, its middleware dedicated for a very flexible processing of AIS messages, and the trajectory prediction algorithm for vessels that helps to identify implausible AIS data. Finally, we report evaluation results obtained from the station prototype that is installed close to the port of Rostock, Germany.

I. INTRODUCTION

The shipping industry contributes significantly both to the economy in general and to the transportation sector in particular. There are over 50,000 cargo ships operating around the world in 2020 [1]. The shipping industry faces significant challenges related to vessel accidents and to high consumption of fossil fuels during long sea journeys. Tracking a vessel’s location and predicting its course help to prevent marine accidents and to optimize the consumption of fossil fuel.

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a tracking system for marine traffic monitoring and collision prevention [2]. Vessels transmit their unique identification, position, and voyage information as AIS messages using AIS transponders on board. These AIS reports are broadcasted in the Very High Frequency (VHF) range and captured by nearby ships, satellites, and AIS terrestrial receiver stations mounted on shore. AIS is a powerful vessel tracking system. But, its efficiency and quality can still be improved in two ways.

The first way is extending the AIS network’s coverage by installing more AIS (terrestrial) receiver stations along the vessel’s trajectory. Receiving the maximum number of messages enables an optimal and fine-grained tracking and monitoring. However, AIS messages may still be damaged or faulty due to poor environmental conditions and/or technical problems. Therefore, the second way is to improve AIS quality by pre-processing received messages and preventing erroneous data to be sent to the tracking server. The latter has two valuable

advantages: a better usage of the often scarce communication bandwidth and a reduced server load due to the elimination of faulty messages.

In our contribution, we present the design and implementation of an autonomous and intelligent station for receiving AIS messages. The station has been designed to be installed at remote geographical areas where a lack of both electricity and wired Internet prevented the installation of terrestrial AIS receivers before. In the following, we first introduce AIS in more detail in Sect. II. Section III discusses the station’s hardware and software that are designed to enable a reliable reception and processing of AIS messages while minimizing manual maintenance efforts. In Sect. IV, we describe implemented means including the prediction of a ship’s movement in order to improve the data quality by detecting and filtering out erroneous and/or implausible AIS messages. Finally, Sect. V presents the station prototype and reports first evaluation results, whereas Sect. VI concludes the paper.

II. AUTOMATIC IDENTIFICATION SYSTEM

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) established the International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) which defines minimal standards for vessel operation [3]. Over the years, SOLAS has undergone several amendments to keep up with technical advancements and improve the maritime safety. One of the significant technical additions is the Automatic Identification System (AIS). Among other vessels, for example, all passenger ships as well as cargo ships of more than 300 gross tonnage, that are engaged in international voyages, are required to carry AIS. However, many non-SOLAS vessels such as smaller commercial ships, fishing vessels, and pleasure crafts have also adopted AIS for safety and navigational benefits.

Ships equipped with AIS continuously broadcast essential information via radio in the very high frequency (VHF) range that include their identity, position, course, speed, and navigational status. The data is received by nearby vessels enhancing their situational awareness. This way, vessels can early identify potential collision risks and take timely actions to avoid accidents. Furthermore, AIS signals are also received by terrestrial stations as well as satellites in low orbit enabling to build a comprehensive picture of maritime traffic in coastal

Figure 1. AIS network and communication partners.

regions (e.g., ports and harbors) and to even track ships and goods on the high seas, respectively. Figure 1 depicts the different senders and receivers involved in AIS communication.

The ITU M.1371-5 standard [4] defines 27 different types of AIS messages that are categorized in static and dynamic messages. Static AIS messages contain fixed information about a ship that typically does not change during its voyage. This information helps other vessels and coastal stations to identify the ship (e.g., ship name, IMO number) and to understand its characteristics (e.g., length, width, height of the ship, type of vessel). As the data remains relatively constant over time, it is sufficient to transmit static AIS messages at longer intervals. In contrast, dynamic AIS messages are transmitted at shorter intervals providing realtime and frequently updated information about the ship’s current status (e.g., position report, next waypoint and distance to it) and movement (e.g., speed, heading, rate of turn). This data is of particular interest for tracking a vessel and predicting its course.

Table I
IMPORTANT DATA CONTAINED IN DYNAMIC AIS MESSAGES.

Parameter	Unit/Range	Description
MMSI	30 bits	Maritime mobile service identity (ID)
NAV	Integer (0-15)	Navigational status (e.g., 0 = under way using engine, 1 = at anchor, ...)
LON	1/10000 min (±180°)	Longitude (WGS 84)
LAT	1/10000 min (±90°)	Latitude (WGS 84)
SOG	1/10 kn (0-102.2 kn)	Speed over ground
COG	1/10 deg (0-359.9°)	Course over ground
TH	deg (0-359°)	True heading
ROT	deg/min (±708°/min)	Rate of turn
Time	UTC second (0-59)	Timestamp when report was generated

Figure 2. Raspberry Pi Compute Module 4 with I/O board and AIS hat.

Table I gives an overview about the most important parameters conveyed in dynamic position reports that are used in our subsequent analysis. A vessel is uniquely identified by its maritime mobile service identity (MMSI). The navigational status (NAV) is manually set by the crew describing the ship’s activity such as underway using the engine, engaged in fishing, at anchor, or moored. The current position is reported using geographic coordinates (i.e., longitude and latitude) based on the WGS 84 standard [5] as utilized by the ship’s electronic positioning system (i.e., GPS). Furthermore, the report also includes the vessel’s speed over ground (SOG) and course over ground (COG), its heading (TH) and the rate of turn (ROT) when maneuvering. Finally, a short timestamp is added when the report is generated.

III. AUTONOMOUS AND INTELLIGENT AIS STATION

The primary mean to improve AIS tracking quality and coverage is to install more AIS base stations along coastlines and at strategic locations close to waterways and shipping routes. These (terrestrial) stations receive AIS signals from passing ships and relay the information to other vessels, maritime authorities, and commercial tracking services. However, to fill the gaps in the AIS network, it is often necessary to place the receiver stations in poorly covered remote areas that usually lack urban infrastructure such as electricity supply and wired internet connection. Moreover, these stations need to be as robust and autonomous as possible as manual maintenance and support is very limited there. In the following, we describe the hardware and software setup of our AIS receiver stations designed for autonomous operation in remote areas.

A. AIS Station Hardware

To cope with the missing electricity supply at remote locations, our AIS station uses solar panels and a rechargeable battery to produce and store the power that is required for operation. Internet connectivity is provided by a cellular gateway using 4G (LTE), 3G, or 2G. Alternatively, an option for Internet satellite links also exists. For all the above components, industrial-grade and even ruggedized solutions exist that are freely available on the market. They can easily be purchased, installed, and interconnected.

However, the heart of the AIS station is a mini-computer based on a Raspberry Pi 4. More specifically, we prefer the Raspberry Pi compute module 4 (CM4) [6] over the regular

Figure 3. Internal interprocess communication via publish/subscribe.

Pi model for three reasons: (i) Some compute module variants are shipped with integrated eMMC flash memory for storing the operating system and data freeing us from having to boot the system from external micro SD cards that are often prone to I/O errors. (ii) The I/O board on which the CM4 is mounted provides plenty of interfaces to connect peripheral devices such as the solar charge controller or the Internet gateway. (iii) The I/O board comes with an realtime clock backed by its own battery and even capable to automatically wake up the system. Please note that the Raspberry Pi CM4 with 4 ARM Cortex-A72 cores at 1.5 GHz and up to 8 GB RAM and 32 GB eMMC flash storage is more than capable to monitor the solar charge controller and process received AIS messages before forwarding these to the vessel tracking servers. Nevertheless, it is still energy efficient.

Because of its rich ecosystem of hardware components and software tools, the Raspberry Pi is an ideal platform for prototyping. Figure 2 shows a photo of the CM4 centrally mounted on the I/O board. At the top right, there is the AIS receiver module implemented as a Raspberry Pi HAT, i. e., an extension board attached on the top. The receiver’s coaxial cable leads to the left out of the photo towards the AIS antenna. Finally, all hardware components and peripheral devices, except the solar panels and the antennas, are firmly mounted within a sturdy metal enclosure. Please see Sect. V and Fig. 4 for a description and photo of the installed prototype, respectively.

B. AIS Station Software

Regarding the station’s software, the purpose of the developed middleware is twofold. First and foremost, it is responsible for processing received AIS messages. Second, to increase the station’s autonomy, we invest in monitoring, logging, fault diagnosis, and fault resolution in order to detect and resolve problems as early as possible.

1) *AIS message processing*: The internal communication is based on a publish/subscribe scheme as depicted in Fig. 3. This enables both a very flexible and an extensible organization of processing functions. The AIS signal is received by the Raspberry Pi’s AIS hat. The receiver decodes the message and outputs the data as an NMEA 0183 sentence.

NMEA 0183 [7] is a standard communication protocol used in marine electronics and navigation systems. It defines the format and rules for exchanging data between various marine electronic devices and instruments, such as GPS receivers, depth sounders, autopilots, and other navigational equipment including AIS. Data is exchanged in the form of *sentences*. A sentence only contains printable ASCII characters and ends with a carriage return (CR) and a line feed (LF) character. Individual data fields in a sentence are separated by commas. A received AIS message, for example, may look as follows:

!AIVDM,1,1,,B,13:0<s0v1NPnGF8O6>R3Kjih8<0v,0*18

The first field **!AIVDM** tells that this is an AIS message received from an other (not the own) vessel. The sixth field starting with **13:0<s...** contains the actual AIS payload that requires further processing. At the end, separated by *****, there is the NMEA checksum. The other fields (not printed in bold) are of lesser importance and, for example, deal with fragmented messages, multi-sentence messages, payload padding, or tell the VHF channel on which the message was received.

After the AIS signal has been decoded, the NMEA sentence is published to a broker for internal data distribution. We use MQTT [8] as publish/subscribe protocol implemented by the Eclipse Mosquitto broker [9]. Several processing pipelines are subscribed to the received NMEA sentences. As a first step, each pipeline adds a tag block to the sentence. The tag block contains a Unix timestamp as well as the identifier of the AIS station that received the message. If no further processing is needed, the data sentence can be forwarded via cellular network to the AIS tracking servers in the cloud. In the case that Internet is currently unavailable, the tagged messages are temporarily buffered on stable storage until the network connection has been restored. Then, all messages are sent at once. The processing pipeline on the bottom left in Fig. 3 does not forward AIS messages. Instead, it saves them to a log file which is very helpful for debugging.

On the one hand, the depicted processing pipelines offer a big potential for optimization. For instance, adding the tag block could be factored out into an own process. On the other hand, this leads to more interdependencies between

processes and pipelines which is actually undesired. Although the pipelines may share a lot of their source code, each pipeline is started with its own processes so that it can be individually managed, i. e., switched on and off without disturbing others. Furthermore, it is also easier to adapt or evolve a single processing pipeline, for example, if the API of a tracking server changes or further message processing steps are added as described in Sect. IV.

2) *Monitoring and maintenance*: On-site service and maintenance of AIS receiver stations often require costly field trips, in particular, if these are installed at very remote locations. Of course, not all field trips can be avoided as hardware components need to be replaced when they fail. But, many field trips can be better planned if aged and worn-out, but still working components are proactively replaced before they actually fail. However, in order to detect potential problems early on, a lot of health data about the AIS station and its hardware components need to be collected. For this purpose, the developed station middleware monitors various health metrics such as the battery level, the current energy production and consumption, the CPU temperature and load, currently available RAM and disk space, and others. These metrics are then combined in a message, periodically published, and sent to a monitoring server where the detailed health status is graphically displayed and statistically analyzed. In particular, it is possible to compare current health metrics with those from the past or from a different station. This way, well-informed maintenance decisions can be made.

For many software problems, remote support is often sufficient. An administrator remotely logs into the station, looks for the cause of the problem, and is usually able to fix it. This may also include installing new software features. However, for this to work, a reliable network connection is crucial. Moreover, if the network connection is left in an unusable state, this becomes a critical failure as neither the station nor the tracking servers are reachable anymore. To counter this, the station middleware periodically checks the network connection by contacting several servers in the cloud. If none is reachable, the middleware starts a systematic procedure for fault diagnosis and fault resolution. The latter may range from a simple retry after some time over a reinitialization of certain software and hardware modules up to a whole station reboot.

IV. DATA QUALITY

Another way to improve vessel tracking is to increase the quality of available AIS information by filtering out faulty and implausible data as early as possible. For this purpose, we have integrated two additional processing steps in the AIS message pipelines from Fig. 3. Both steps are discussed below.

A. Checksum Calculation

Damaged messages are filtered out by verifying their checksum. We compute the checksum of the received AIS data and compare it to the checksum stored in the message. If both disagree, the message is silently discarded. This is a simple, but very effective measure.

Figure 4. Prototype of the AIS station installed at the campus in Warnemünde close to the port of Rostock, Germany.

B. Trajectory Prediction

An undamaged AIS message is decoded into its constituent parameters including Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI), location given by longitude (LON) and latitude (LAT) coordinates, speed over ground (SOG), and course over ground (COG). All parameters are checked for plausible values. For example, the AIS station is only able to receive messages within a certain maximum range. Thus, any coordinates farther away can be rejected as implausible.

Beyond those simple checks, we also predict a vessel's movement based on previous position reports. For this purpose, we convert the ship's reported geographic position LON and LAT into Cartesian coordinates x and y and set V and γ to SOG and COG, respectively. Then, the state vector

$$X = (x, y, V \cdot \cos(\gamma), V \cdot \sin(\gamma))^T$$

describes the vessel's movement in a compact form where $V \cdot \cos(\gamma)$ and $V \cdot \sin(\gamma)$ are the x and y component of the vessel's velocity, respectively. We then follow [10] to setup and employ a Discrete Kalman Filter (DKF) [11] in order to predict the vessel's trajectory. When a new AIS message is received, we estimate the ship's position based on the DKF. If the Euclidean distance between this estimation and the received coordinates from the message exceeds a certain threshold, the reported position is also rejected as implausible.

V. PROTOTYPE AND EVALUATION

We prototypically implemented our autonomous AIS receiver station and installed the prototype at the campus in Warnemünde which lies close to the port of Rostock, Germany. Figure 4 shows a photo of the station prototype mounted on the rooftop. The antenna is installed at a height of 22 meters from the sea level and is able to track vessels at a maximum distance of about 55 kilometers. This is sufficient to cover the whole ferry route from Rostock to Gedser, Denmark, across the Baltic Sea. Figure 5 shows a map with the captured ship traffic on the river Warnow and on the Baltic Sea around Rostock for October 11th, 2022.

The station is working reliably for over a year now. For example, from September 11th to October 11th, 2022, the station prototype received, processed, and forwarded 16,209,960

Figure 5. Ship traffic around Rostock captured by the AIS station prototype on October 11th, 2022.

correct AIS messages. On some days within this period, up to 7% of all received messages were filtered out as damaged. Implausible messages occurred far less frequently. They are usually caused by temporary inaccuracies in a ship’s electronic positioning system (i.e., GPS) and introduce noise in the vessel tracking data. As dealing with noisy data on the tracking servers is much more costly, the implemented movement prediction on the station provides a substantial benefit.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented the design and implementation of an autonomous and intelligent AIS receiver station. Its hardware consists of commercial off-the-shelf components. Hardware and software are designed to minimize maintenance efforts well suited for installations at remote locations that are not easily accessible. The middleware enables a very flexible processing of AIS messages and is extensible to add future

processing and monitoring tasks. Beyond simple checksum and sanity checks, we implemented a trajectory prediction algorithm for vessels based on a Kalman filter in order to identify implausible AIS data. The station’s prototype has been installed near the port of Rostock and reliably delivers AIS data for over a year now.

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